

PRINCIPLES OF DEVELOPMENT OF LEADING STAFF MANAGEMENT COMPETENCE

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Annotation The article describes the regulation of personal economic, material and financial aspects of the development of personnel potential, the content and essence of management potential, what constitutes the structure of management potential, the ethical aspects of management culture, the knowledge and qualities necessary for management.

Key words: personnel potential, job satisfaction, management potential, management culture, moral aspects, knowledge and virtues, intelligence and humanity, goodness and happiness, strength and potential.

Today's complex issue is regulation of personal economic, material and financial aspects of personnel development. This factor ensures job satisfaction after feeling affection → demand → legal guarantee. As the fourth of the twelve principles that the master Amir Temur followed in the administration of the kingdom, it can be said based on the experience of "keeping all categories of personnel in the service based on laws and regulations and satisfied with their positions and careers" [1] that the effective provision of this will ultimately lead to the stability and development of the state. leads to provision.

Management capacity is naturally a phenomenon with an integral and complex structure, consisting of relevant knowledge about management, spiritual qualities and psychophysiological foundations. This is explained by the view of management potential by scientists as a set of abilities, qualities and characteristics necessary for the performance of management activities. For example, the Russian researcher Yu.S.Zentsova understands the management potential of a person as the possibility and ability to solve tasks in the field of organizing and managing the activities of other people [2], researcher Yu.Melnik, the management potential is the opportunities and abilities of a person to implement management and at the same time related to accumulated management experience, he says. In his dissertation, the Russian scientist S. L. Saibel defines management potential as a set of service-related personal qualities, opportunities, and abilities that are used by the leader to solve management tasks and achieve set goals [3]. According to O.F.Alexina, management potential is a set of theoretical knowledge, practical experience and individual characteristics of employees who perform management functions [4].

It seems that most scientists generally answer the question of what constitutes the structure of management capacity as a set of qualities, opportunities or abilities, but its content, that is, what those qualities include, is not clearly indicated. In some cases, the answer is based on some (mobilization, motivation) tasks performed in management activities. To do this, to approach the issue from a structural-functional point of view, that is, to determine what concrete qualities are required in the performance of each task in management, remains one of the urgent tasks facing science.

According to the teachings of Confucius, who emphasized the moral aspects of management culture, among the values of management, gaining the trust of the people and ensuring order in the society are important. In this regard, he said that government is the existence of sufficient food, sufficient weapons and public trust. To the question of what should be understood by the state administration, the philosopher answers as follows: the ruler is the ruler, the servant is the servant, the father is the father, the son is the son, it is clear that for him, discipline is a value that should be paid attention to in management activities. Achieving these goals, in his opinion, requires saving resources, correcting distortions in the system, and mobilizing people to work.

In turn, the fulfillment of these tasks depends on the effective use of appropriate methods and tools, and the rich legacy of scholars is still worth studying. For example, Confucius, who firmly believed in governing the state by virtue, said that if it is governed by law and regulated by punishment, then the people will be vigilant, but will not know shame. If it is ruled by virtue, if it is regulated by custom, the people will not only be ashamed, but at the same time will show obedience. Also, the great thinker "Imam Moturidi's life wisdom, "Live in sympathy with the country, so that the people will always be with you", should be imprinted in the mind, heart and actions of every minister and every leader" [5] is relevant even for today.

If there is enough intelligence and humanity, and if they rule with strict discipline, but if the people are not called to action with the help of traditions and customs, there is no perfection yet, he says. At the same time, according to him, people follow a well-behaved leader even without orders. The main principle of this activity, according to him, is that when people are involved in work, they participate in management without getting angry. In this regard, "inspire enthusiasm with your personal example." Don't know how to rest. Be an example to your subordinates, don't blame them for their minor shortcomings, promote worthy and capable people", are methodological guidelines that have

not lost their relevance even today. Also, according to him, in order to be able to implement the above, a leader and manager "must have the ability to carefully observe, intelligence and, of course, moral qualities such as honesty, love for people, conscientiousness and honesty" [6]. Thus, Confucius believes that it is best to approach management activities based on values and traditions. State management with a deep understanding of them is praised as a guarantee of social order and stability. When working with people, on the basis of psychological, moral and economic approaches, activation of their voluntariness, enthusiasm, spiritual and spiritual power, thereby ensuring social stability, is considered one of the traditional values. At the same time, of course, the ideological limitation in this doctrine is manifested in a negative attitude towards the non-traditionalism required by the goal of development of management, from which it is permissible to draw a correct conclusion.

According to Farabi, "in addition to knowledge, the ruler must have the following: first, the necessary strength and capacity to lead the society to goodness and true happiness; secondly, it is necessary to be able to convince people of the correctness of the chosen path to happiness" [7]. In fact, Farabi says that "it is not possible for everyone to lead others, to raise them to the level of happiness. A person who does not have the ability to make someone happy, to inspire them to do necessary work, and is incapable of doing this work, such a person cannot be a leader at all" [8]. It should be noted that along with the knowledge and qualities necessary in management, the thinker also reveals the law of their formation.

It is known that each of us has seen not only how a leader behaves, but also how he behaves when he believes in himself and when he does not believe in himself. Unfortunately, an insecure leader changes his decision as the situation changes. Employees working under such a leader do not see support in the person of their leader, their days in the organization seem temporary. Moreover, such a leader is not able to negotiate with others. Because a person who does not believe in his own personality and abilities cannot inspire confidence in others. One of the characteristics of a great leader is restraint and patience. The emotional balance of the leader is expressed in the fact that he does not allow conflicting emotions to overflow in his inner world and is calm in his mood.

It is known that the leader lives among people and in the midst of different emotions. Consequently, the negative or positive feelings of the surrounding people have the characteristic of being "contagious" in daily communication. Therefore, in volatile and conflicting situations, the leader should not only not be

influenced by the emotions of others, but should also be able to influence others with his balance and restrained emotions. This quality of the person is determined on the one hand by the innate nature of the nervous system, and on the other hand, it depends on the acquired life experience. For the moderation of the nervous system, the leader should take care of his health. Organizing work in a rational way, that is, paying more attention to the positive aspects of work, wisely eliminating unpleasant situations, being around more close friends, spending time in a mood of passion for physical education and useful activities, strengthens the body's ability to resist any stress, and also improves the body's ability to work. serves to restore the ability.

Another quality necessary for a leader to perform management activities effectively is the desire for success. A leader should be able to set a goal and try to fulfill it. In general, human desire can be divided into two categories:

- 1) striving for success;
- 2) avoid defeat.

When a difficult and critical situation arises, some people think about achieving success by solving this situation, while others avoid the "disaster" as much as possible in order to avoid losses. These are two different approaches to the same situation, whose owners are people with different personalities. Since the effective leader belongs to the first category, he quickly solves problems and moves forward towards his goal. A person of this category can usually take risks. When the time comes, he breaks down the big goal into smaller pieces and envisions the outcome behind each smaller goal. However, such a factor is not always easy to implement. Therefore, a leader must have a character that can take risks and is not afraid of danger. A person who lives with a passion for achieving a goal always wants to be informed about the results of his activities. The situation related to work allows one to analyze the content of one's life by receiving information from one's activities.

Another necessary quality for effective management is responsibility and confidence in solving tasks. In times of economic and social difficulties, instilling confidence in one's partner, guaranteeing the next job and, on top of that, getting it done, is an important quality for a modern leader. In this process, leadership becomes integrated with entrepreneurial activity and the concept of trust becomes central.

Independence is one of the qualities that not only increases the leader's reputation, but also leads him to the main goal in a difficult situation. A leader should strive to own his vision, observation skills and personal perspective. It is

true that a leader should listen to his colleagues as well as his advisers, but the decision and its implementation rests with the leader. Therefore, independence in thinking and behavior is one of the main factors of effective management. However, independence should not turn into stubbornness. For this, the leader must always align his initiative with the goals of the organization or team. It's no secret that no person is born with the traits on this list. All of these are the product of human abilities and socio-historical living conditions. Manifestation of such qualities in leadership requires a person to work regularly and on himself, to constantly create an example in his perception and to imitate him. Above, we mentioned the personality traits necessary for effective management activities. Knowing these qualities, the leader's desire to form them in himself, without a doubt, takes his management skills to higher levels and accelerates the direction of the organization to the intended goal. But from the point of view of methodology, a leader is not just a set of qualities, at the same time, there are more powerful forces that embody and harmonize these qualities, with the participation of which there can be a leader image consisting of a certain combination of qualities.

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